
60. Scientific project management

AS IN SO MANY transformational events in life, we can look back and question the series of largely random events that led up to them. So it is that I found myself, in 1981 and aged just 26, and barely a year after completing my PhD in radio astronomy, appointed as ESA's Project Scientist for the recently adopted Hipparcos mission.

With an estimated cost of around €400M, and a conceptual design existing largely only on paper, it was the start of a series of numerous technical and organisational challenges, that I could not have anticipated. Looking back, would I have handed such a young and inexperienced scientist this sort of responsibility? I'm not sure that it would happen today, although I also suspect that, given the right skill set and character, young people can often be precisely those with the commitment, passion, energy and adaptability to succeed.

What is the skill set, or character profile, needed to drive such a project through to success? The short answer, perhaps, is to counter with the rhetorical question: *How long is a piece of string?*

IN MY AREA OF EXPERTISE, space science, ESA appoints two key people, from two separate departments within the Directorate of Science, and with two distinct reporting lines within it.

The Project Manager, with a team of typically 20–25 engineers/managers reporting to them, supervises the industrial design and development of the satellite, and carries overall responsibility for the mission's cost and schedule. *Project* team members are rarely knowledgeable about the mission's *science*. Their collective success is judged on some ill-defined combination of the mission's ultimate science achievements, and its cost and schedule compared to the original targets.

The Project Scientist tends to work alone in ESA, or at most with a very small team. Calling instead upon the enormous skill set in the wider scientific community beyond ESA, but with limited financial authority to assemble or direct their activities, the task of the Project Scientist is to act as the guardian of the scientific goals of the mission at the time of its adoption by ESA.

THEY DO THIS by interfacing with the scientific community representing the mission's scientific requirements on the one hand, and with the project team on the other. They communicate and translate the mission's scientific goals into technical requirements, mediating discussions between the two groups when requirements must be prioritised or relaxed, for example when cost over-runs are at stake. And they establish, coordinate, and ultimately deliver whatever the associated scientific/community supporting structure is required, for example in the scientific preparations in advance of launch, and in the preparation of the data processing facilities required to interpret the satellite data.

Throughout my time in ESA, from 1980–2009, and having been Project Scientist for two of these missions, and latterly as senior adviser on others, there was never a specification of the detailed responsibilities of this central role. It was often argued, for example, that any one mission is generally very different from any other.

At one extreme, some science missions comprise a *spacecraft*, which is managed and procured by the project team in conjunction with the industrial prime contractor, and this spacecraft system supports a set of *instruments* which are developed, built, supplied by, and eventually operated by scientific collaborations across Europe and often beyond (having been delivered to and integrated by the industrial prime contractor, according to interfaces specified by the project team).

At the other extreme, where the final mission performance is more acutely determined by the combination of spacecraft and payload performances, the payload (or experiment) may also be procured under the responsibility of the ESA project team. Examples of the former include missions like FIRST, SOHO, and Mars Express. Examples of the latter include both Hipparcos and Gaia.

With many of these responsibilities, interfaces, and final products only loosely defined, and with limited financial influence on both the project team and the scientific community, how can the Project Scientist best work to achieve some optimum balance between scientific performance, overall cost, and ultimate schedule?

ALTHOUGH PROJECT MANAGEMENT in these two areas (under the Project Manager, and Project Scientist) have many aspects in common, the boundary conditions and objectives are usually very different. In the following, I will focus on some comments relevant to the *scientific* management of these large projects.

I will argue that (1) there are skill sets that the appointed scientific leader should possess in order to best optimise the prospects of success, and (2) there are lessons that can be learned from previous large space projects, and indeed from wider sociological studies of how people and teams best work together.

DETAILED CONSIDERATION of these aspects, along with the various caveats and nuances, would be lengthy and, like management in general, somewhat subjective. In the following, I will make some fairly simplified statements to introduce the challenges.

Firstly, scientists in the area of space science and astrophysics (and probably in physics more widely) undergo an education and training period, involving undergraduate, post-graduate, and post-doctoral studies, leaving the individual with a solid foundation in, for example, mathematics, computing, and a broad knowledge of physics, thus equipping them with the necessary foundation for a career in research.

Many of these well-qualified scientists soon start to work in wider collaborations, and often as parts of teams designing, building, and operating large and complex instruments and experiments, and taking responsibility for sub-systems or even managing the entire project. But rarely, in my experience, are these people offered advice, training, or some accumulated wisdom on how to manage projects, and how to manage people.

I mean, it's something we are either good at or not, and certainly something we can pick up along the way, right? Or we might take heed of respected Dutch astronomer Henk van de Hulst (1918–2000), who pointed out that *'doing science on your own is hard; doing it in collaboration with others is even harder!'*

I HAD THE BENEFIT, from day 1, of interfacing with the Hipparcos project team through the first ESA Hipparcos Project Manager, Franco Emiliani. Twenty years my senior, and already experienced from his work on Space-lab and others, I learned the techniques of Gantt charts and milestone trend analysis, work breakdown structures, configuration control and action item tracking.

Emiliani was interested in the scientific goals of Hipparcos, and despite our differences in age and experience (and pay grade!), we quickly formed a working practice underpinned by mutual respect, he of the goals of the scientists who would be spending decades of their working lives on the project, and me of the technical and schedule constraints that the ESA project team and the industrial contractors were working under.

Following standard practice, I set up a scientific advisory team composed of a dozen European scientists expert in the various aspects of the field: not simply representatives of the end users of the astrometric data, but those whose understanding extended to the technical aspects and to the data treatment. The team worked exceptionally well over the 17-year life of the mission, even though my early appointment of the group was in the days before I'd heard of Belbin's Teams and Apollo Teams.

AS FOR THE ATTRIBUTES of an ideal scientific project leader, they are easy enough to specify, but a challenge to identify in any one individual! They should be particularly well organised, and with familiarity with all instrument or mission aspects. As well as this 'big picture', allowing informed trade-offs when necessary, the leader should be a scientist of some repute, but willing to put an active research career on hold in order to manage properly a large and complex task.

Integrity is paramount, and an ability to take timely and frequently difficult decisions is clearly required. The ability to anticipate and confront problems before they become disastrous is particularly important. Communication skills are crucial, and taking the time to inform all team members, track actions, and liaise with funding authorities and political decision makers is essential.

Of course not all of these 'ideal attributes' will be met in any one individual in practice!

LET ME FINISH with just a few suggestions to anyone managing a large scientific project:

- (1) establish a clear hierarchical advisory and decision-making structure. The team should cover all relevant project aspects, should not be more than 10–12 people, should loosely adhere to Belbin's Team principles, and should be adjusted as the project phase demands;
- (2) use the regular meetings to exchange information on progress, and to agree on future 'actions' with clear objectives and fixed due dates. Expect these to be adhered to, so as to avoid a knock-on effect on overall schedule;
- (3) establish clear project goals or scientific objectives from the outset, and ensure that all participants sign up to them. Beware of 'requirement creep' where new objectives are adopted as the project develops, and make realistic trade-offs between scientific aspirations and technological capability as needed;
- (4) establish a top-level project plan from the start, with major milestones covering the entire project duration;
- (5) view the entire project as an inter-related system, all of whose elements must be considered from the outset. As one simple example, do not wait until an instrument is designed and defined before addressing the user interfaces, and the data treatment.

It's an incomplete list, of course, but hopefully conveying the spirit of passing on accumulated wisdom.